

Institute of Vocational Studies

Himachal Pradesh University

(NAAC Accredited 'A' Grade University)

Summer Hill, Shimla-171005, India.

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Prof. Sonia Khan

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr. Rajinder Kumar has completed his Doctoral work entitled "Tourism Education in India: Perception of Academicians and Industry Professionals", under my supervision and guidance at the Institute of Vocational Studies, Himachal Pradesh University, Summer Hill, Shimla, India.

To the best of my knowledge and belief, it is an original piece of research work, based upon facts and data collected by the scholar on his own and it is worthy for consideration for award of Degree of Doctor of Philosophy in Tourism Studies.

Place:

(Sonia Khan)

Dated:

Supervisor